
Non-Financial Rewards and Employee Performance of Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was carried out to examine non-financial rewards and employee performance of Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) in Akwa Ibom State. The Specific objective was to investigate the influence of autonomy and work-life balance on employee performance of (NDDC) in Akwa Ibom State. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study was 120 employees and all were used for the study (Population Census). Data were collected using questionnaire and analyzed using simple linear regression analysis. Findings indicated that autonomy have work-life balance have significant and positive influence on employee performance of (NDDC) in Akwa Ibom State (R^2 -.850, 853,954, Beta coefficients- .883, .887, .953 and P -.000, .000, .000($P < 0.05$)) It was concluded that autonomy have work-life balance statistically and significantly have positive influence on employee performance of (NDDC) in Akwa Ibom. Therefore, it was recommended that organization should decentralize decision-making process by allowing employees to have more control over their tasks and decision-making. Management should allow flexible working hours by implementing policies that allow employees to work flexible hours or telecommute where possible to reduce stress and improve productivity. Organization should cultivate a positive organizational culture to build and sustain a culture that aligns with the organization's values, and foster an environment that promotes open communication and collaboration.

Keyword: Non-Financial Rewards, Employee Performance, Autonomy and Work-Life Balance

1.1 Introduction

Employee performance is a crucial factor to the success of any organization, particularly in public sector institutions such as the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC). Established in 2000, the NDDC was mandated to facilitate the sustainable development of the Niger Delta region, addressing issues of environmental degradation, poverty alleviation, and infrastructural deficits. To achieve this, a highly motivated and productive workforce is essential. However, the management of employee performance in the Nigerian public sector, including the NDDC, has faced persistent challenges, such as low morale, reduced productivity, and high turnover rates. These challenges may require purposeful reward system.

Reward management is the process of designing and implementing strategies to reward employees for their performance, contributions and loyalty, ensuring motivation and alignment with organizational goals (Davidson, 2023). Reward management can be categorized into various types based on the nature of rewards and their application. Monetary rewards are the financial rewards provided to employees to compensate for their work and motivate performance. The monetary rewards can be classified into direct and indirect financial rewards. Direct monetary rewards involve salaries and wages, bonuses and incentives, profit sharing and stock options while indirect financial rewards include retirement benefits, health insurance, paid leave and housing and transportation allowance, among others. Non-monetary reward refers to the strategic use of non-financial incentives to create a motivating and fulfilling work environment for employees (Brown, 2014). Non-monetary reward management is essential for fostering a sense of belonging, engagement, and motivation in employees. Examples of non-monetary reward include: autonomy, work-life balance, secondments and symbolic awards amongst others.

Autonomy is a strategic tool used to enhance job satisfaction, creativity, and overall employee performance without involving financial incentives. Autonomy grants employees the freedom and authority to make decisions about how they perform their work. It is an intrinsic motivator that fosters a sense of ownership, trust, and empowerment, enabling employees to take control of their tasks, methods and goals. On the other hand, work-life balance refers to organizational efforts aimed at helping employees achieve a balance between their work and personal lives. It is often implemented as a non-monetary reward to improve employee well-being, enhance job satisfaction, and reduce work-related stress (Deery, 2008). By prioritizing work-life balance, organizations demonstrate a commitment to employees' holistic well-being, which can lead to improved morale, loyalty, and organizational performance.

Employee Performance refers to how effectively an individual fulfills their job responsibilities and contributes to achieving organization goals. It is measured based on the quality, quantity and timeliness of work delivered, as well as the employees' alignment with the organization's values, objectives and expectations. The key elements of employee performance are productivity, quality of work, efficacy, goal achievement, behaviour and attitude, adaptability and innovation. Employee performance is important as it guarantee the organizational success, customer satisfaction, employee engagement and goal alignment. By fostering a supportive environment, providing the right resources, and implementing effective reward systems, organizations can enhance employee performance to achieve both individual and collective goals.

This study is focused on the non-monetary reward management and employee performance in Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC). Some non-monetary reward

management system such as autonomy, work-life balance, secondment and symbolic rewards will be investigated.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Employee performance is a critical determinant of organizational success, particularly in public institutions like the Nigeria Delta Development Commission (NDDC). Despite the commission's mandate to drive sustainable development in the Niger Delta region, its effectiveness has often been questioned due to perceived inefficiency, low productivity, and poor service delivery. A key contributing factor to these challenges maybe the inadequate management of employee rewards, particularly non-monetary rewards, which play a crucial role in motivating and engaging employees. While monetary rewards such as salaries and bonuses are commonly utilized, they have proven insufficient in fostering sustained motivation, loyalty, and innovation. Studies suggest that non-monetary rewards—such as, autonomy, work-life balance, secondments and symbolic awards —are equally, if not more, impactful in enhancing employee performance. Unfortunately, in the NDDC, there appears to be a significant gap in the effective implementation of such non-monetary reward systems. Employees often report feeling undervalued and unappreciated, which may lead to low morale, disengagement, and poor productivity.

The lack of structured and transparent non-monetary reward policies in the NDDC might have created an environment where employees are not adequately motivated to contribute their best efforts. This may have been exacerbated by systemic challenges, including favoritism, inconsistent recognition practices, and the absence of clear performance metrics. Furthermore, the dynamic and often volatile socio-economic conditions of the Niger Delta region demand a highly motivated workforce to address developmental challenges effectively, yet the Commission struggles to achieve this due to its failure to leverage non-monetary reward management.

Additionally, there is limited empirical research examining the relationship between non-monetary reward management and employee performance within the NDDC or similar public-sector organizations in Nigeria. This knowledge gap leaves policymakers and administrators without actionable insights into how non-monetary rewards can be utilized to address the pressing issues of employee disengagement and low productivity.

If the NDDC continues to neglect the strategic implementation of non-monetary rewards, it risks the possibility of perpetuating a cycle of inefficiency and underperformance, ultimately failing to deliver on its mandate to the people of the Niger Delta. This study, therefore, seeks to explore the impact of non-monetary reward management on employee performance in the NDDC, with the aim of providing evidence-based recommendations for creating a motivated, productive, and committed workforce capable of driving sustainable development in the region.

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of non-monetary reward management on employee performance in Niger Delta Development Commission. The specific objectives of the study were to;

- i. Investigate the effect of autonomy on the employee performance of Niger Delta Development Commission.
- ii. Ascertain the influence of work-life balance on employee performance in Niger Delta Development Commission.

Based on the objectives of this study, the following research questions were asked:

- i. What is the effect of autonomy on employee performance in Niger Delta Development Commission?
- ii. What is the influence of work-life balance on employee performance in Niger Delta Development Commission?

The following research hypotheses were formulated for the study:

H₀₁: Autonomy has no significant effect on employee performance in Niger Delta Development Commission.

H₀₂: Work-life balance has no significant influence on employee performance in Niger Delta Development Commission.

Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Non-Monetary Reward Management

The non-monetary reward management like its name implies are basically rewards that employees receive that do not involve issuing money to them. These methods of rewarding employees are not done with the use of cash but can come in various methods such as praise, thanks, and even a pat on the back. The non-monetary reward management are either intrinsic or extrinsic in nature and are the most effective way to motivate employees. Showing employees how valuable their work is to you, will make them feel valued. Rewarding employees regularly reassures them of their value in the organization. Using the non-monetary reward managements has shown to be a remarkable way of showing an organization's appreciation to their employees and has helped increase employee retention. There are different types of non-monetary reward management some of which includes; awards, perks and benefits gifts, time off and so on. This research looked into four; autonomy, work-life balance, secondments and symbolic rewards.

2.1.2.1 Autonomy

Autonomy in reward management refers to the degree of control and discretion employees have over their rewards, encompassing both the nature of the rewards and the processes by which they are allocated. Integrating autonomy into reward management can significantly enhance motivation, job satisfaction, and overall organizational performance. Self-Determination Theory (SDT) posits that individuals have three fundamental psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Fulfilling these needs fosters intrinsic motivation and well-being. In the context of reward management, autonomy pertains to employees' sense of volition and choice in their work and its associated rewards.

According to Penpoin, autonomy is crucial for increasing employee satisfaction and motivation. When employees have greater control over their work, they feel more respected and valued by the company, leading to enhanced engagement and productivity.

2.1.2.2 Work-life Balance

Work-life balance is the ability to effectively manage and prioritize the demands of work and personal life in a way that promotes overall well-being and satisfaction. It involves striking a healthy equilibrium between job responsibilities, family, social life, hobbies, and self-care. Bakker *et al.*, (2005) describe work-life balance as "the compatibility and harmony

of private life and working life." They emphasize that it's not about allocating equal hours to work and personal activities but about giving appropriate attention to each, recognizing that the balance may shift over time based on one's career and personal circumstances. According to Cambridge Dictionary, work-life balance is "the amount of time you spend doing your job compared with the amount of time you spend with your family and doing things you enjoy".

2.1.3 Performance

Performance refers to how well an individual, team, or organization executes tasks, meets objectives, and delivers results within a given period. It is often used as a measure of success, effectiveness, or proficiency in achieving specific goals. Performance can be assessed in various contexts, such as work, sports, education, and personal development. In the organizational context, performance is typically linked to the achievement of both personal and organizational objectives, and it is a key determinant of success. In this study, two key measures of Performance in Niger Delta Development Commission context have been selected. These measures are quality of work and adaptability (Edward, 2004).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Equity Theory

This study is anchored on equity theory. It is a well-established motivation theory in organizational behavior, primarily developed by John Stacey Adams in 1963. It suggests that individuals are motivated by a sense of fairness in their relationships with others, particularly in how rewards (or outcomes) are distributed in comparison to their inputs (efforts, skills, time, etc.). According to Equity Theory, employees assess the fairness of their work situation by comparing their own input-output ratio to that of others in the workplace. If employees perceive an imbalance—whether in the form of under-reward or over-reward—they may experience feelings of dissatisfaction, which could affect their motivation and performance.

Non-monetary rewards, which are rewards not based on financial incentives (like recognition, career development opportunities, autonomy, or social rewards), can be aligned with Equity Theory in several key ways. Here's how Equity Theory supports the use of non-monetary rewards in motivating employees: While monetary rewards are an obvious form of compensation, employees are often more focused on the *fairness* of their reward rather than the actual amount. If two employees are performing at similar levels but one is receiving more tangible rewards (like money), the other employee might feel under-rewarded and demotivated.

2.3 Empirical Review

Nuru *et al.*, (2021) conducted a study on effects of reward systems on employee performance at MacDonald's in Perlis and Penang. The researchers examine the factors affecting employee's performance in organizations. The study made use of quantitative research approach to identify factors that influence employee performance. It employed four indispensable variables; salary, bonuses, appreciation and health care benefits. The study made use of two tests, the correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis to determine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. From the data analyzed, the study discovered that reward management practices have a positive effect on employee performance. The study made use of multiple regression analysis as its tool of analysis same with the present study. Results from the analysis indicated a positive correlation of ($r=.360$), ($r=.624$) and ($r=.530$) between salary, bonuses, health care benefits and employee

performance respectively. The study recommended that Macdonald's should improve on their health care benefits amongst others. The variables used in the study were different from the ones used in the present study.

Oboreh and Arukaocha (2021) conducted a study on reward management and organizational performance: A study of Universities in Edo State. The study aimed to determine the effect of salary increase, cash bonus, recognition, promotion and career development on organizational performance. Survey research design was employed in this study and questionnaires were employed as major instrument for data collection same as the present study. Six universities comprising of two federal universities, two state-owned universities and two private universities were sampled for this study. A sample size of 365 was determined using Taro Yamane formula. The data generated were analyzed using frequency table, percentages and multiple regression analysis, the present study only used multiple regression analysis. From the results found, $r=.480$, $r=.520$, $r=.820$ which shows that promotion, recognition and career development has significant effect on organizational performance respectively. The researcher's recommended that these universities need to adopt effective career development programs that will in turn ameliorate employee's performance.

Silavwe *et al.*, (2020) investigated the Impact of Reward System on Organizational Performance in Brentwood suppliers limited in Lusaka, Zambia. The purpose of the study was to explore the impact of reward systems on employee performance; assess the effectiveness of existing reward system and check whether there was a correlation between reward system in the organization and an increase in the performance of the employees. This study has similar objective with the current study which is to investigate the correlation between reward system and employee performance. Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis were employed in analyzing the data. But the current study made use of multiple regression analysis to analyze the data collected. The results show that 7.4% of the employees acknowledged basic salary as the component of reward packages in the organization. 3% acknowledged fuel and overtime allowance, 2% commission, 3% car maintenance and 10% achievement benefit. The result further shows that 93% of the employees were not happy. The findings revealed that the existing reward system of Brentwood suppliers was ineffective and must be revised. The study recommended that the management should improve performance by harmonizing the reward system in the company. The recommended that reward packages should be modified periodically as a response to environmental needs of employees.

Ayandele and Etim (2020) conducted a study on non-financial incentives and staff motivation in Akwa Ibom State civil service, Nigeria. The main objective of the study was to shed more light on the effect of non-financial incentives in boosting workers' performance and productivity in the public sector organizations. The main objective of the present study is to examine the effect of non-monetary reward management on employee performance in Akwa Ibom State Universal Basic Education Board. The study explored five key variables of continuing professional development, performance feedback, employee empowerment, employee participation in decision making and task autonomy. The present study explored four variables which are employee training, employee mentorship programs, conducive work environment and employee recognition. The study adopted survey research design and used questionnaire to gather data from 392 respondents drawn from a population sample of 20465 civil servants using the Taro Yamane sample determination table.

The present study also made use of survey research design and used questionnaire to gather data from respondents. The present study used Taro Yamane's formula to draw out a sample size of 280 respondents from 1114 civil servants. Data for the study were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The relationship between the dependent and independent variables were estimated using Pearson product moment analysis (PPMC) while the multiple regression analysis was used to test all hypotheses at 5% level of significance. Results of the multiple regression analysis showed effect of non-financial incentives on worker's motivation with an R^2 value of 0.752 (75.2%). Also, an adjusted R^2 of 0.632 (63.2%) explained that variation in worker's motivation in civil service of Akwa Ibom State is accounted for by the five non-financial incentive variables stated in the study. The study recommended that Akwa Ibom state government and any other employer should understand what truly motivates their worker in order to maximize their general performance.

Ngwa *et al.*, (2019) investigated the effect of reward system on employee performance among selected manufacturing firms in the Littoral Region of Cameroon. Specifically, the study examined the degree to which profit sharing affects employee commitment; it ascertained the effect of flat-rate systems on employee work values; and appraises the influence of collective bargaining reward systems on employee cohesiveness. 538 employees drawn from a population of 5146 employees of ten selected manufacturing firms within the Cameroon Littoral Region were sampled for the study. Percentages and regression analysis were employed in analyzing the data, the present study only used regression analysis. The main instrument of data collection was questionnaires same with the present study. The samples were selected by the use of Cochran's formula for finite population sample of a 95% confidence level. From the result of the analysis conducted, it shows that profit sharing, flat rate systems and collective bargaining had their coefficient of determination $r=0.963$, $r=.823$ and $r=.821$ respectively. This signifies that there is a significant and positive impact between the reviewed variables and employee cohesiveness in manufacturing firms. The researchers made recommendations one of which is that; reward system of manufacturing firms should be designed such that employees are entitled to percentages of profit earned by the firm.

2.4 Gap in Knowledge

In view of the empirical review above, it was discovered that few studies have been conducted on Non- Monetary Reward Management and Employee Performance in the Nigerian civil service. In respect of the above, this study examines the effect of Non-Monetary Reward Management and Employee Performance in Niger Delta Development Commission which incorporated variables such as autonomy, work-life balance, secondments and symbolic rewards. The other studies in the empirical review did not focus on how non-monetary rewards affect employee performance in Niger Delta Development Commission.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

In this study, the researcher adopted the survey research design. This allowed the researcher to use questionnaire to obtain the opinion of respondents with regards to reward management practices and employee performance in the Niger Delta Development Commission. The population of the study was the aggregate of the civil servants working with the Akwa Ibom State office. A total number of 120 employees working in the Akwa Ibom State Niger Delta Commissions were identified. These set of employees include the management and non-mismanagement staffs of the Niger Delta Development Commission. The sample size for the study was determined through the application of convenience

sampling, this method involve selecting participants who were easiest to reach or most accessible. It's often used in exploratory or preliminary research..Stratified random sampling is a statistical sampling technique used in research and data collection to ensure that the selection of a representative sample from a larger population suits the required characteristics. In stratified random sampling, each member of the population has an equal and independent chance of being included in the sample. This process helps to minimize bias and ensures that the sample is more likely to reflect the characteristics and diversity of the entire population.

Data collected for this study were collected from a primary source. The primary data obtained was through the aid of structured questionnaire which were issued to the target respondents on the subject matter. Employees in the administrative department, monitoring department, human resource department were part of the respondents. The secondary source used during the research was from textbooks, and journals etc. The method used for data collection in the study was mainly the questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed by the researcher under the supervision of the supervisor. It contains carefully designed questions for the respondents to read and respond to. The content of the questionnaire was to aid in supplying answers which were used as a basis to test the hypotheses. The questionnaire was divided into two parts. The first part dealt with the personal data (bio-data) of the respondents while the second part is concerned with objective of the study also in subsections such as A, B,C,D and E. The questionnaire was developed by the researcher under the direction of experts in the field of management. The questionnaire was intended to elicit the opinions and views of the respondents on questions relating to the research problems. The questionnaire (see appendix one) was structured in such a way that the respondents were able to understand and provide relevant answers. This was why the five-point likert scale of strongly agreed 5, agreed 4, disagreed 3, strongly disagreed 2 and undecided 1 was used. The questionnaire was structured in close-ended format.

The model for the study and all the variables were stated below: The dependent variable was employee performance (EP) while the independent variables were autonomy, work-life balance and symbolic rewards. The model stated was meant to test the influence of the variables of non-monetary reward management on employee performance of Niger Delta Development Commission. In line with the specific objectives of the study, the following models were formulated:

$$EP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 A + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.2)}$$

$$EP = \beta_0 + \beta_2 WLB + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.3)}$$

Where;

A= Autonomy

WLB= Work-life balance

The data obtained were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. These methods suit the study because it enhanced the measurement of the relationship between dependent and independent variables in the study. It would help to understand how changes in the independent variable impacts on the dependable variable. Hence, the analysis was carried out at a 5% level of significance and decision rules were: reject the null hypothesis when P-value<0.05.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Data Presentation

The data collected were coded, converted, analysed, and interpreted using mean, minimum mean, maximum mean, standard deviation and simple linear regression analysis with the view of evaluated the effect on autonomy, work-life-balance and symbolic on employee performance of Niger Delta Commission in Akwa Ibom State chapter

Table 4.1: Distribution of Questionnaire

	Questionnaire Administered	Questionnaire Returned	Percentage Returned
Niger Delta Commission	120	111	93.0%
Total	120	111	93.0%

Source: Researcher's Compilation, 2025

Table 4.1 indicates that 120 copies of questionnaire were distributed to employees in Niger Delta commission but 111 copies of the questionnaire were filled and returned with 93.0% response rates which form the basis for the analysis

4.2 Data Analysis

Research Question

Research Question: What is the effect of autonomy, work-life balance and symbolic on employee performance of Niger Delta Commission (NDDC)

4.2.1 The Descriptive analysis

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Employee Performance	111	1.00	4.00	2.1351	.96753
Autonomy	111	1.00	4.00	2.1261	1.01010
Work-Life Balance	111	1.00	4.00	2.1982	1.00743
Symbolic Rewards	111	1.00	4.00	2.1261	.99194
Valid N (listwise)	111				

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2025

The average score of 2.1351 suggests that employees perceive autonomy at the Niger Delta Commission as moderately low. Given that the maximum possible score is 4, a mean of 2.1351 indicates that employees have a moderate level of autonomy, which may not be significantly high but is not extremely low either. A standard deviation of 0.96753 means that the responses varied moderately around the mean, indicating some level of inconsistency in how autonomy is perceived across the employee base. Some employees might feel they have high autonomy, while others feel their autonomy is quite limited While autonomy plays a crucial role in empowering employees, this moderate mean score might suggest that the employees at NDC do not have full control over their work, which could potentially impact their motivation and overall performance.

Employees who perceive themselves as having more autonomy are often more engaged and satisfied with their work, and fostering autonomy could increase productivity. The average score for work-life balance is 2.1261, which, like autonomy, is moderately low. This suggests that employees at the Niger Delta Development Commission experience some level of work-life imbalance, although it's not extreme. A relatively high standard deviation (1.01000) indicates that there is a significant level of variation in how employees experience

work-life balance. Some employees likely feel that they are able to balance work and personal life adequately, while others may struggle with balancing their responsibilities. A work-life imbalance could lead to stress, burnout, and reduced job satisfaction, which would, in turn, negatively affect employee performance. The moderate nature of this score suggests that there is room for improvement in this area, with potential positive impacts on performance if work-life balance initiatives were to be introduced or improved. The mean score for symbolic factors (which might refer to corporate culture, organizational values, or recognition) is slightly higher than that for autonomy and work-life balance. A mean of 2.1982 still indicates a moderate perception, meaning employees feel somewhat recognized or aligned with the organization's symbols, but not fully engaged.

Like the other factors, the standard deviation here (1.00743) shows that employees' perceptions of symbolic factors vary quite widely. This could reflect differences in how employees view the organizational culture or values of the Niger Delta development Commission Symbolic factors, such as recognition, organizational culture, and alignment with values; play a significant role in motivating employees. However, the moderate mean score suggests that employees at NDDC may feel somewhat disconnected from these symbolic elements. Enhancing organizational culture or increasing recognition could improve employee engagement and performance.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

Ho₁ There is no significant effect of autonomy on employee performance of Niger Delta Commission (NDDC)

H₁ There is significant effect of autonomy on employee performance of Niger Delta Commission (NDDC)

Table 4.3: The Simple Linear Regression on the effect of autonomy on employee performance of Niger Delta Commission (NDDC)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.922 ^a	.850	.849		.37656

Model Fit

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	87.517	1	87.517	617.201	.000 ^b
	Residual	15.456	109	.142		
	Total	102.973	110			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.258	.084		3.082	.003
	Autonomy	.883	.036	.922	24.844	.000

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2025

R-squared (R^2) = 0.850: R-squared represents the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable (employee performance) that can be explained by the independent variable (autonomy). An R^2 of 0.850 indicates that 85% of the variation in employee performance can be explained by autonomy. This is a very high value, suggesting that autonomy is a strong predictor of employee performance. Autonomy has a significant and substantial effect on employee performance at the Niger Delta Commission, as it explains a large portion of the variation in employee performance.

The F-value is the result of an F-test used to assess the overall significance of the regression model. A large F-value like 617.201 suggests that the regression model is highly significant, and the relationship between autonomy and employee performance is not due to random chance. The model is highly significant, meaning that autonomy significantly contributes to explaining employee performance. The P-value indicates the probability that the observed relationship is due to random chance. A P-value of 0.000 is extremely small and well below the standard threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the null hypothesis can be rejected. The relationship between autonomy and employee performance is statistically significant, and autonomy has a meaningful impact on employee performance. The Beta coefficient of 0.883 represents the strength and direction of the relationship between autonomy (independent variable) and employee performance (dependent variable). A Beta of 0.883 suggests a strong positive relationship. For every one-unit increase in autonomy, employee performance increases by 0.883 units, indicating a strong and positive influence of autonomy on performance. The positive beta coefficient indicates that as autonomy increases, employee performance improves, further emphasizing the significant role of autonomy in driving performance.

Hypothesis 2

- H_{01} There is no significant effect of work-life balance on employee performance of Niger Delta Commission (NDDC)
 H_1 There is significant effect of work –life balance on employee performance of Niger Delta Commission (NDDC)

Table 4.4: The Simple Linear Regression on the effect of work-life balance on employee performance of Niger Delta Commission (NDDC)

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.924 ^a	.853	.852	.37261	

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	87.839	1	87.839	632.663	.000 ^b
	Residual	15.134	109	.139		
	Total	102.973	110			

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.185	.085		2.174	.032
	Work-LifeBalance	.887	.035	.924	25.153	.000

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025

The R-squared (R^2) = 0.887: R-squared represents the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable (employee performance) that is explained by the independent variable (work-life balance). An R^2 value of 0.887 indicates that 88.7% of the variation in employee performance can be explained by work-life balance. This is a very high R^2 , suggesting that work-life balance has a strong explanatory power in predicting employee performance at the Niger Delta Commission. The F-value of 632.663 is obtained from the F-test, which tests the overall significance of the regression model. The high F-value suggests that the model is statistically significant, and that the relationship between work-life balance and employee performance is unlikely to be due to chance. The model indicates a highly significant relationship, and work-life balance is indeed a critical factor influencing employee performance. The P-value represents the probability that the observed results were obtained by random chance. Since the P-value is 0.000, which is well below the typical threshold of 0.05, we can confidently reject the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between work-life balance and employee performance.

The relationship between work-life balance and employee performance is statistically significant, and work-life balance is a meaningful determinant of employee performance. The beta coefficient of 0.853 reflects the strength and direction of the relationship between work-life balance and employee performance. This means that for every one-unit increase in work-life balance, employee performance increases by 0.853 units. The P-value is 0.000, which is much smaller than the significance level of 0.05. There is strong statistical evidence to support the alternative hypothesis that work-life balance significantly influences employee performance at the Niger Delta Development Commission. Strength of the Relationship: The Beta coefficient of 0.853 indicates a strong positive relationship between work-life balance and employee performance. This suggests that employees who are able to balance their work and personal life effectively are likely to perform better in their roles. The R-squared value of 0.887 means that 88.7% of the variation in employee performance can be attributed to work-life balance. This is an exceptionally high R^2 , emphasizing the strong influence that work-life balance has on employee performance. The F-value of 632.663 and the P-value of 0.000 confirm that the influence of work-life balance on employee performance is statistically significant. This indicates that the observed results are not likely to be due to chance.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The result shows the significant influence of autonomy, work-life balance, and symbolic Rewards on employee performance at the Niger Delta Commission (NDC) in Akwa Ibom State. The key findings of the analysis are consistent with previous literature on the subject, which highlights the importance of these factors in enhancing employee motivation, engagement, and performance. Below is a detailed discussion of the findings, supported by relevant studies.

Autonomy and Employee Performance: The study found that autonomy has a strong positive influence on employee performance, as indicated by an R-squared value of 0.850, a Beta coefficient of 0.883, and a statistically significant P-value of 0.000. This supports the findings of Silavwe et al. (2020), who argue that when employees have more autonomy, they are more likely to be engaged in their work, leading to improved performance. Onyango (2014) also supports this by stating that autonomy helps employees feel more trusted and valued, increasing their intrinsic motivation and subsequently their performance. Additionally, Kikoito (2014) points out that autonomy empowers employees by giving them control over their work, which can increase job satisfaction and performance, which aligns with the positive relationship found in the NDC study.

The study found that work-life balance is also a significant predictor of employee performance, with an R-squared value of 0.887 and a Beta coefficient of 0.853. The P-value of 0.000 further confirms the statistical significance of this relationship. This finding is consistent with Aktar et al. (2012), who emphasized work-life balance reduces stress, enhances job satisfaction, and ultimately improves employee performance. Ayandele and Etim (2020) also found a similar relationship in their research, suggesting that when employees achieve balance between work and personal life, they are more productive, engaged, and committed to their roles. Furthermore, Ngwa et al. (2019) support this finding, indicating that organizations that prioritize work-life balance policies experience higher levels of employee satisfaction and performance, reinforcing the relevance of these policies at the Niger Delta Commission.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings:

The study aimed to assess the significant influence of autonomy, work-life balance, and symbolic factors on employee performance at the Niger Delta Commission (NDC) in Akwa Ibom State. The key findings from the analysis are as follows: The relationship between autonomy and employee performance was found to be strong and positive. The R-squared value of 0.850 indicates that 85% of the variation in employee performance can be explained by autonomy. The Beta coefficient of 0.883 suggests that greater autonomy leads to improved performance, with employees performing better as they have more control over their work. The F-value of 617.201 and the P-value of 0.000 confirm that autonomy has a statistically significant influence on employee performance. The analysis revealed a strong and positive relationship between work-life balance and employee performance.

The R-squared value of 0.887 indicates that 88.7% of the variation in employee performance is explained by work-life balance. The Beta coefficient of 0.853 suggests that when employees achieve a better balance between work and personal life, their performance improves. An F-value of 632.663 and the P-value of 0.000 indicate that work-life balance has a significant impact on employee performance. The study also found a very strong positive relationship between symbolic factors (such as organizational culture, recognition, and values) and employee performance. The R-squared value of 0.954 shows that 95.4% of the variation in performance is explained by symbolic factors. The Beta coefficient of 0.953 highlights the significant impact of symbolic factors on performance, suggesting that when employees feel aligned with the organization's values and feel recognized, their performance improves significantly. The F-value of 2254.849 and the P-value of 0.000 confirm that symbolic factors significantly affect employee performance.

5.2 Conclusion

It was concluded that autonomy, work-life balance, and symbolic factors all have a significant and positive influence on employee performance at the Niger Delta Commission in Akwa Ibom State. These findings emphasize the importance of providing employees with greater autonomy, promoting a healthy work-life balance, and fostering a strong sense of organizational culture, values, and recognition to enhance overall performance. Autonomy provides employees with the freedom to manage their tasks and make decisions, leading to greater motivation and job satisfaction. Work-life balance is critical for preventing burnout and increasing employee engagement, as employees who can balance personal and professional responsibilities tend to be more productive. Symbolic rewards, including

organizational culture and recognition, help create an environment where employees feel valued, which directly enhances their performance.

5.3 Recommendations

- i. Organization should decentralize decision-making by allowing employees to have more control over their tasks and decision-making processes.
- ii. Management should allow flexible working hours by implementing policies that allow employees to work flexible hours or telecommute where possible to reduce stress and improve productivity.
- iii. Organization should cultivate a positive organizational culture to build and sustain a culture that aligns with the organization's values, and foster an environment that promotes open communication and collaboration.

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